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Non-LTE error assessment for CAIRT - Technical Note

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Abstract

This supplement provides a non-LTE error assessment for the Earth Explorer 11 candidate mission CAIRT (the Changing-Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography Explorer). Section 1 outlines the non-LTE assessment strategy that followed in order to assess non-LTE related errors in CAIRT's targeted geophysical (L2) quantities. Section 2 briefly describes the non-LTE models used in the retrievals and the related uncertainties. A table with a summary of the uncertainties is provided. Section 3 provides a table identifying the non-LTE processes leading to errors overcoming CAIRT's L2 data requirements. The estimations were made based on Linear Performance simulator (LPEv2) simulations and the Extended Reference Scenario (ERS).

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1 Strategy for non-LTE error estimations

In order to estimate the non-LTE errors in CAIRT's retrievals, we went through the following steps. First, we revised the current status on the non-LTE collisional processes and their kinetic rates used in the non-LTE models included in the retrievals. We then identified the major current uncertainties related to those processes that might significantly affect the retrievals of the species considered in CAIRT. The estimations of the propagation of the individual non-LTE uncertainties onto retrievals were afterwards performed for the ERS scenario using the 2D Linear Performance Estimator (LPEv2) within SciRec (see Sect. 1.3 in DEL-08-CAIRT-Ph0SciRec). We finally grouped the information on the CAIRT L2 target errors associated to the individual non-LTE parameters in the context of goal and threshold L2 requirements. We specifically highlight non-LTE related uncertainties that may compromise the achievement of CAIRT's requirements.

2 NLTE models and related uncertainties

In this section, we describe the non-LTE models used in CAIRT's retrievals, that is, CO₂, O₃, NO, CO, H₂O, O₂ and CH₄ non-LTE models. We have taken as the basis the general non-LTE GRANADA model described in Funke et al. (2012). The major improvements/updates with respect to that study can be summarized as:

- The spectroscopic data (Einstein coefficients, energies of high-energy vibrational levels, etc.) have been updated for most species except O₃ with the HITRAN 2016 database (Gordon et al., 2017).
- Atmospheric input data has been taken from the ERS climatologies.
- (Near-) surface related parameters (cloud coverage and altitude, surface albedo, etc.), relevant for the calculation of upwelling radiative fluxes, have been updated.
- For some molecules, more energy levels have been included.
- Some collisional rates affecting the population of the emitting levels, as detailed in the following sections.

2.1 NLTE model of CO₂

2.1.1 Collisional rates affecting the CO₂ 15 μm levels (TLOS retrieval)

There have been no major changes in the CO₂ NLTE model with respect to the description in Funke et al. (2012) regarding the levels emitting at 15 μm, from where temperature is retrieved in CAIRT. The changes are mainly related to the CO₂ levels emitting near 4.3 and 2.7 μm. Even if CAIRT does not measure these emissions and the effect of these changes on the CO₂ 15 μm level populations is not significant, they affect the population of the N₂ levels, and, therefore, eventually the CO levels. Thus, we provide detailed information on these updates. These levels are described in Jurado-Navarro et al. (2016) and are summarised below. One of the major update is several collisional rates that were retrieved from the analysis of MIPAS spectra near 10 and 4.3 μm (see Jurado-Navarro et al., 2015). In particular, they retrieve the rate coefficients and their temperature dependence in the 130-250 K range of the following processes: CO₂(v_d, v_3)+N₂ ⇌ CO₂(v_d, v_3-1)+N₂(1) with $v_d = 2v_1 + v_2=2, 3$ and 4; CO₂($v_1, v_2, l, 1, r$)+M ⇌ CO₂($v'_1, v'_2, l', 1, r'$)+M with $\Delta v_d=v'_d - v_d=0$ and $\Delta l=0$; and with $\Delta v_d=0$ and $\Delta l \neq 0$. In addition they also retrieved the thermal relaxation of CO₂(v_3) into the v_1 and v_2 modes, e.g., CO₂(v_d, v_3) + M ⇌ CO₂(v'_d, v_3-1) + M with $\Delta v_d=2-4$ and $\Delta v_3=-1$; and the efficiency of the excitation of N₂(1) by O(¹D) (see Table 1).

Figure 1: Schematic diagram showing the collisional rates considered affecting the CO₂ levels (see Table 1). Panel a) shows (in red) the processes $k_{vv,0}$, $k_{vv,1}$, $k_{vv,2}$, $k_{vv,3}$, $k_{vv,4}$, k_{vt} , and $k_{O(^1D)}$ of the major CO₂ isotopologue. The deactivation of N₂(1) by O(³P), k_O , is also shown. The energy levels follow the (v_d, v_3) notation with $v_d = 2v_1 + v_2$. Panels b) and c) show the k_{F1} (in red) and k_{F2} (in green) processes for the $(v_d=2, v_3=1)$ and $(v_d=4, v_3=1)$ levels, respectively. $k_{F2'}$ and k_{F2} in panel b) correspond to the processes between (10011–02211) and (10012–02211), respectively. N₂(1) and O(¹D) energy levels are not at scale. After Jurado-Navarro et al. (2015).

The rates of processes 1 and 2 are very similar to those in Funke et al. (2012). Processes 3–7 were not measured before and the values retrieved by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2015) are significantly different from those used in Funke et al. (2012).

The k_{vt} collisional rates (processes 8a and 8b) retrieved by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2015) are a factor of 0.82 smaller than those used in Funke et al. (2012). This factor was further revised by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2016) in the inversion of MIPAS CO₂ V5 to a value of 0.7 because of their revision of the concentration of O(¹D), and has been maintained in the retrieval of CO₂ V8.

The rate of process 9, $k_{O(^1D)}$, retrieved by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2015) does not differ from that used Funke et al. (2012). The same was used in the retrieval of MIPAS version V5 of CO₂ (Jurado-Navarro et al., 2016). The most recent values is that used in the retrieval of MIPAS CO₂ V8, with $f=1.08$ (see Table 1), motivated by the revision of the O(¹D) concentration.

The collisional deactivation of N₂(1) with atomic oxygen, O, k_O , has also been updated. Due to a bug in the GRANADA code, this rate was used in Funke et al. (2012) with a factor of 5 larger than listed in Table 5 of that work. It was updated to a value of $6.4 \cdot 10^{-15} (T/300)^{2.9} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2015), further with the value of $4.5 \cdot 10^{-15} (T/300)^{1.5} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ in the inversion of MIPAS CO₂ V5 by Jurado-Navarro et al. (2016), and more recently with the value listed in Table 1 in the inversion of CO₂ V8.

The retrieved rates were obtained with a much better accuracy than were known before and they have very important effects on the atmospheric limb radiance in the 10, 4.3 and 2.7 μm spectral regions.

An additional process (#11 in Table 1) was included in the model, the V–V v_3 collisional coupling of the ($v_1+v_2=1,2$) states for the (minor) isotopologues 2 to 6 (HITRAN notation) with the v_3 state of the major isotope. This has some effects on the 4.3 and 2.7 μm radiation emitted by the hot isotopic 4.3 and 2.7 μm bands.

A few more improvements with respect to Funke et al. (2012) in these CO₂ model levels are:

- A code error, affecting the populations of the CO₂(010) and CO₂(020) levels (15 μm levels) of isotopologue 628 was also fixed.
- The near-IR solar flux was increased in 1.7% for the 2.7 μm bands; and was reduced in 0.2% for the 4.3 μm bands.
- The Curtis matrices corresponding to the three stronger 2.7 μm bands of the major isotopologue were performed by line-by-line radiative transfer.
- The angular integration of the transmittances of the 2.7 μm bands was improved by using 8 points instead of 4.
- The more recent spectroscopic HITRAN 2016 database is used for this molecule.

The major effects of all these changes are larger vibrational temperatures (in 1–2 K) of the levels emitting near 10 and 4.3 μm above around 60 km.

Table 1: Energy transfer processes affecting the CO₂ levels.

No.	Rate	Process	Rate coefficient (cm ³ s ⁻¹)
1	k_{vv0}	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2(1); v_d = 0$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 4.64^*, \alpha = 0.64^*$
2	k_{vv1}	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2(1); v_d = 1$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 4.64^*, \alpha = 0.64^*$
3	k_{vv2}	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2(1); v_d = 2$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 5.02 \pm 0.22, \alpha = 1.0$
4	k_{vv3}	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2(1); v_d = 3$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 5.61 \pm 0.22, \alpha = 0.6$
5	k_{vv4}	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2(1); v_d = 4$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 5.64 \pm 0.09, \alpha = 0.6$
6	k_{F1}	$\text{CO}_2(v_1, v_2', 1) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_1', v_2', 1) + \text{M}; \Delta v_d = 0, \Delta l = 0$ e.g., $\text{CO}_2(10011) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(10012) + \text{M}$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 7.04 \pm 0.33, \alpha = 0.0$
7	k_{F2}	$\text{CO}_2(v_1, v_2', 1) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_1', v_2', 1) + \text{M}; \Delta v_d = 0, \Delta l \neq 0$ e.g., $\text{CO}_2(02211) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(10012) + \text{M}$, or $\text{CO}_2(10011) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(02211) + \text{M}$	$k_0 \cdot 10^{-13} (300/T)^\alpha, k_0 = 5.57 \pm 0.20, \alpha = 1.2$
8a	$k_{vt,a}$	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3)^{\dagger} + \text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d', v_3 - 1) + \text{N}_2; \Delta v_d = 2-4$	$f \cdot [1.10 \cdot 10^{-15} + 1.14 \cdot 10^{-10} \exp(-72.3/\sqrt{T}) + 2.3 \cdot 10^{-40} T^9], f = 0.70 \pm 0.13$
8b	$k_{vt,b}$	$\text{CO}_2(v_d, v_3) + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2(v_d', v_3 - 1) + \text{O}_2; \Delta v_d = 2-4$	$f \cdot [1.82 \cdot 10^{-15} + 3.10 \cdot 10^{-11} \exp(-63.3/\sqrt{T}) + 2.0 \cdot 10^{-31} T^6], f = 0.70 \pm 0.13$
9	$k_{O(1D)}$	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O}(^1D) \rightarrow \text{N}_2(1) + \text{O}$	$f \cdot \epsilon \cdot 2.1 \cdot 10^{-11} \exp(115/T); \epsilon = 0.2 \times 6.8, f = 1.08 \pm 0.15$
10	k_O	$\text{N}_2(1) + \text{O}(^3P) \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{O}$	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-15} (T/300)^{2.9}$
11	$k_{vv,iso}$	$\text{CO}_2^i(v_3 = 1) + \text{CO}_2^j(v_1, v_2, 0) \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2^i + \text{CO}_2^j(v_1, v_2, 1)$ with $2v_1 + v_2 = 1, 2$	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \sqrt{T}$, for $i = 1$ and $j = 3-6$ $2.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \sqrt{T}$, for $i = 1$ and $j = 2$

([†]) $v_d = 2v_1 + v_2$. *Used but not retrieved by Funke et al. (2012).

2.1.2 Uncertainties in CO₂ non-LTE parameters

The primary source of temperature error in the upper mesosphere and beyond is attributed to uncertainties in non-LTE modeling, primarily stemming from three collisional rates, and the atomic oxygen and the carbon dioxide abundances. Their uncertainty may result not only in systematic non-LTE temperature errors, but also in their propagation to other retrieved species.

Building upon the insights of García-Comas et al. (2008), corroborated by García-Comas et al. (2023), we have adopted the following error margins for the kinetic rates affecting the CO₂ levels:

- CO₂-M-vt: We assumed a 30% uncertainty in the quenching of CO₂(ν_2) states via collisions with N₂ and O₂, including the temperature dependence. This uncertainty is in agreement with the values for this rate shown in Figs. 6 and 7 of García-Comas et al. (2008).
- CO₂-O-vt: Several laboratory measurements of the rate of CO₂- ν_2 quenching by atomic oxygen are grouped around a rate about 4 times smaller than the atmospheric measurements, which do not support that lower value and clearly point to a higher rate. Figure 9 of García-Comas et al. (2008) summarize with great detailed the available information of this rate, that suggests an uncertainty of 50%.
- CO₂-CO₂- ν_2 -vv: Based on the values reported by Huddleston and Weitz (1981) and Dang et al. (1983) and the considerations in García-Comas et al. (2008), we assumed a 20% uncertainty for the ν_2 vibrational energy exchange between CO₂ molecules.
- CO₂-M- ν_3 -vt: We use an uncertainty of 15% for the thermal relaxation of CO₂(ν_3) into the ν_1 and ν_2 modes, corresponding to the retrieval error of this rate from MIPAS analysis (Jurado-Navarro et al., 2016).
- CO₂-N₂- ν_3 -vv: We adopt an overall uncertainty of 5% for the vibrational energy exchange of CO₂ ν_3 states with N₂ (processes 1–4 of Table 1), based on the estimated retrieval errors for these rates from MIPAS analysis (Jurado-Navarro et al., 2016).

2.2 O₃ NLTE model

For O₃ we also take as a starting point the general description of the GRANADA non-LTE model (Funke et al., 2012). The major changes included in the NLTE model since then regarding the O₃ model are described in López-Puertas et al. (2018, 2023), and are summarised below. Table 2 list the most important non-LTE processes. The collisional processes (1-4) have been adapted from Table 7 in Funke et al. (2012). The exponent a in the k_1 rate has been updated from 2.3 to 2.4 following (?). This, though, has a small effect on the O₃ ν_1 and ν_3 vibrational temperatures and also on the retrieved O₃.

The collisional deactivation of O₃(ν_1, ν_2, ν_3) (process 2c, k_d) was erroneously implemented in Funke et al. (2012) with a rate of $3.1 \times 10^{-15} (T/300)^{1/2}$. This bug was corrected in the retrieval of O₃ in MIPAS V5 (López-Puertas et al., 2018) by including the expression listed in Table 7 of Funke et al. (2012) but, as suggested by Menard et al. (1992), limited to a minimum value of $4 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at temperatures below 200 K (see Table 2). Although this change in the rate coefficient is rather large, its impact on the O₃(ν_3) vibrational temperature is very small, as it is dominated by the relaxation to ν_2 .

The chemical quenching of vibrationally excited O₃ by O (process 3) was neglected in the retrieval of MIPAS O₃ V5, as suggested by West et al. (1978), and so have been kept since. This implies larger O₃(ν_3) vibrational temperatures.

The total quenching of O₃(ν_1, ν_3) by O (process 4a), includes also the collisional relaxation by O, process 4 in Table 2. This rate was not altered in the retrieval of MIPAS O₃ V5 but, as the resulting mesospheric O₃ was larger than in other instruments measurements (López-Puertas et al., 2018), it has been decreased by a factor of 2 in the retrieval of MIPAS O₃ V8, setting it up in $4.65 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (see

Table 2: Collisional and radiative processes affecting the O₃ vibrational levels.

No.	Rate	Process	Rate coefficient (cm ³ s ⁻¹) [†]
1	k_1	$\text{O}_2 + \text{O} + \text{M} \rightarrow \text{O}_3(v_1, v_2, v_3)$	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-34} (T/300)^a$, $a = 2.4$
2		$\text{O}_3(v_1, v_2, v_3) + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{O}_3(v'_1, v'_2, v'_3) + \text{M}$	
2a	$k_{d,2}$	Δv_1 or $\Delta v_3 = -1$, and $\Delta v_2 = 1$	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-14} \sqrt{T} \exp(-23.8/\sqrt[3]{T})$
2b	k_2	$\Delta v_1 = \Delta v_3 = 0$ and $\Delta v_2 = -1$	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-12} \sqrt{T} \exp(-51.0/\sqrt[3]{T})$
2c	k_d	Δv_1 or $\Delta v_3 = -1$, and $\Delta v_2 = 0$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-15} (T/300)^7$; $4 \cdot 10^{-16}$ for $T < 200$ K
2d	k_r	Any Δv_i	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-11} (300/T)^{0.78} 10^{a+b, \ddagger}$
3	k_{chem}	$\text{O}_3(v_1, v_2, v_3) + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}_2 + \text{O}_2$	Not included
4	$k_{vt,O}$	$\text{O}_3(v_1, v_2, v_3) + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}_3(v'_1, v'_2, v'_3) + \text{O}$	
4a	$k_{vt,O,d2}$	Δv_1 or $\Delta v_3 = -1$, and $\Delta v_2 = 1$	$4.65 \cdot 10^{-12}$ for $v_1+v_3=1$; Landau-Teller scaling for $v_1+v_3 \geq 2$
4b	$k_{vt,O,2}$	$\Delta v_1 = \Delta v_3 = 0$, and $\Delta v_2 = -1$	$3 \cdot 10^{-12}$ for $v_2=1$; Landau-Teller scaling for $v_2 \geq 2$

[†]Except for k_1 that is cm⁶s⁻¹. Note that the energy of the O₃(v_1, v_2, v_3) level is larger than that of O₃(v'_1, v'_2, v'_3).

[‡] $a = -\max[0, (\Delta E - 61)/40]$; $b = \min[0, 2 - (|\Delta v_1| + |\Delta v_2| + |\Delta v_3|)]$.

Table 2). This rate is still within the uncertainties of the laboratory measurements, although at the lower limit measured by West et al. (1976) (see the discussion in López-Puertas et al., 2018). This value is also consistent with the more recent measurements of the thermal relaxation of the lower energy v_2 mode in collisions with O (process 4b) at room temperature of $2.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-12}$ cm³s⁻¹ obtained by Castle et al. (2014).

2.2.1 Uncertainties in O₃ non-LTE parameters

The major systematic non-LTE error source of mesospheric O₃ derived from high resolution spectra near 9.6 μm are the O₃ quenching rate by O and the uncertainty of the concentration of nighttime O in the 85-100 km region. Uncertainties in the rates of O₃ quenching by N₂ and O₂, O₃ photolysis and the O+O₂+M three body recombination are also significant. Apart for the O uncertainty (described in Sect. 2.7), we have assumed uncertainties in the kinetic rates as suggested by López-Puertas et al. (2018):

- **O3-O-vt**: The uncertainty in the chemical quenching/collisional deactivation of O₃(v_1, v_3) by O (processes 4a and 4b in Table 2) can be assumed as 50%, based on the measured error from West et al. (1976).
- **O2+O+M**: We have considered uncertainties of 10% for the error in the three-body reaction rate of O₃ formation (process 1 in Table 2), according to the current literature.
- **O3+M**: We assumed a 20% uncertainty of the thermal relaxation of the O₃(v_1, v_3) levels with N₂ and O₂ (process 2 in Table 2), also based on the available literature.
- **O3+hν**: The error of the O₃ photo-absorption coefficient required in the O₃ photochemical model, was estimated in 7%.

In addition, the other major error source for the mesospheric nighttime O₃ is the uncertainty in the concentration of nighttime O in the 85-100 km region.

2.3 NO NLTE model

Updates include an extension of the set of considered rotational levels from $J \leq 45.5$ to $J \leq 55.5$. Concerning the rate constants used in the modeling of collisional and chemical processes, we have incorporated several updates with respect to those listed in Funke et al. (2012). First, for the collisional relaxation of NO vibrational states with O we have adopted the quasi-classical trajectory results by Caridade et al. (2008) for the $\nu > 1$ rates, however, scaling them to the measured value of Hwang et al. (2003) for the $\nu = 1$ state. This change affects mainly thermospheric NO populations, however, the impact on the $5.3 \mu\text{m}$ retrieval is very small.

Second, for the reaction $\text{N}(^4\text{S}) + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO} + \text{O}$ we now use rate coefficients from the JPL Evaluation no 18 (Burkholder et al., 2015). The rate constant for the reaction $\text{N}(^2\text{D}) + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO} + \text{O}$ is taken from Vitt et al. (2000). The nascent distributions of vibrationally excited NO from both reactions have been adopted from the more recent theoretical values of Sultanov and Balakrishnan (2006) instead of those of Duff et al. (1994), resulting in 3–6% larger excitations. Again, the impact of this change on the $5.3 \mu\text{m}$ retrieval is very small and restricted to the thermosphere.

Third, the rate coefficients for the reaction of NO_2 with O is now taken from the JPL Evaluation 18. The nascent distribution of vibrationally excited NO from this reaction has been taken from Smith et al. (1992), resulting in a 40% lower efficiency for production of the $\nu \geq 1$ compared to the previous values taken from Kaye and Kumer (1987). This change induces a 2–5% increase of the retrieved NO abundance in the upper stratosphere around 40 km, which brings it into better agreement with the values expected from photochemical equilibrium.

2.3.1 Uncertainties in NO non-LTE parameters

Regarding kinetic rates needed in the non-LTE model calculations, we consider uncertainties of five key processes specified below and discussed in Funke et al. (2023):

- **NO-O2**: Rates for the deactivation of vibrationally excited NO in collisions with O_2 are taken from Wysong (1994). They report an uncertainty of individual rates for different vibrational states in the 10–17% range. Here, we assume an overall uncertainty of 20% for this process.
- **NO-O-vib**: We also assume a 20% uncertainty for the multi-quantum relaxation of vibrationally excited NO in collisions with O. This uncertainty corresponds to the reported error of the laboratory measurements for the relaxation rate for the $\nu = 1$ state (Hwang et al., 2003). The rotational temperatures, used to describe the rotational nascent distribution of excited NO in the reverse process, are 25% lower than the kinetic temperature (Sharma and Duff, 1997), with an assumed uncertainty of 10%. For the nascent spin temperature, which is set to 200 K in our calculations (Lipson et al., 1994), we assume an uncertainty of 50 K.
- **RT-beta**: A relevant parameter for $5.3 \mu\text{m}$ retrievals is the spin-propensity factor β which controls the spin conservation of NO in rotational-translational collisions with N_2 , O_2 , and O (see Bermejo-Pantaleón et al., 2011). The considered value of 0.9, however, is well constrained by atmospheric observations. We therefore assume a relatively small uncertainty of 5%. Larger uncertainties are expected for the rotational relaxation rates in NO-O collisions which have not been directly measured so far. Here, we assume an uncertainty of 50%.
- **NO2+O**: The assumed uncertainty of the production rate of vibrationally excited NO from the $\text{NO}_2 + \text{O}$ reaction is 40% which corresponds to the reported error of the experimental results from Smith et al. (1992).

- **NO₂+hν**: We assume an overall uncertainty of 10% for the production rate of vibrationally excited NO from NO₂ photolysis, which encompasses uncertainties of NO₂ cross-sections, quantum yields and albedo effects.

We do not explicitly consider uncertainties related to the production rates of vibrationally excited NO in the reaction of N(⁴S) and N(²D) with molecular oxygen because the overall uncertainty of this chemical excitation process is dominated by the much larger uncertainties in the N(⁴S) and N(²D) abundances.

2.4 H₂O and O₂ NLTE models

The collisional processes included in the H₂O-O₂ non-LTE models are listed in Tables 3 and 6. Most updates we have done to the models of Funke et al. (2012) were based on our analysis previous to MIPAS version 8 water vapor retrievals. The major changes can be summarized as:

- We consider a new temperature dependence for the rate of quenching of O₂(1) by atomic oxygen (process o.5 in Table 4), as suggested by Pekajovic et al. (2011).
- We derived a new rate for vibrational exchange between H₂O and O₂ (H₂O-O₂-VV; processes 1 and o.1 in Tables 3 and 6, respectively). A value 35% larger than the one used in Funke et al. (2012) was determined from comparisons of daytime and nighttime water vapor measurements.
- We have increased the rate of vibrational exchange between O₂(1) and CO₂(020) (O₂-CO₂-vv) by a factor of 1.5, in accordance with MIPAS measurements.
- We have also revised the the O₂(*v*) model scheme.

Several attempts have been made in the past to determine from atmospheric measurements the rate of V-V O₂(X,1)-H₂O(*v*₂) collisions (*k*₁ in Tables 3 and 4), the quenching of O₂(1) by atomic oxygen (*k*_{o.5} in Table 4), and the O₂(X,1) production from ozone, in particular, after photodissociation. We consider

Table 3: Collisional processes affecting the H₂O vibrational levels.

No.	Process	Rate (cm ³ s ⁻¹)
1	H ₂ O ^{<i>i</i>} (<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ (<i>v</i> -1) ⇌ H ₂ O ^{<i>i</i>} (<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ -1, <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ (<i>v</i>)	$v_2 \times 1.35 \times 10^{-12}$; $v=1,2$ for $i=1$ $v=1$ for $i > 1$
2	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + M (N ₂ , O ₂) ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ -1, <i>v</i> ₃) + M	$v_2 \times 4.1 \times 10^{-14} \sqrt{T/300}$
3	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O(³ <i>P</i>) ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ -1, <i>v</i> ₃) + O(³ <i>P</i>)	$v_2 \times 1.0 \times 10^{-12} \sqrt{T/300}$
4	N ₂ (1) + H ₂ O ⇌ N ₂ + H ₂ O(010)	$1.2 \times 10^{-14} \sqrt{T/300}$
5	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + N ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ +1, <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃ -1) + N ₂	$1.2 \times 10^{-11} \sqrt{T}$
6	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ +1, <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃ -1) + O ₂	$1.1 \times 10^{-11} \sqrt{T}$
7	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + N ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃ -1) + N ₂	$4.6 \times 10^{-13} \sqrt{T/300}$
	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + N ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ -1, <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃) + N ₂	$4.6 \times 10^{-13} \sqrt{T/300}$
8	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃ -1) + O ₂	$3.3 \times 10^{-13} \sqrt{T/300}$
	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ -1, <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂	$3.3 \times 10^{-13} \sqrt{T/300}$
9	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O(³ <i>P</i>) ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃ -1) + O(³ <i>P</i>)	$3.0 \times 10^{-12} \sqrt{T/300}$
	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O(³ <i>P</i>) ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ -1, <i>v</i> ₂ +2, <i>v</i> ₃) + O(³ <i>P</i>)	$3.0 \times 10^{-12} \sqrt{T/300}$
10	H ₂ O ^{<i>i</i>} (010) + H ₂ O ^{<i>j</i>} ⇌ H ₂ O ^{<i>i</i>} + H ₂ O ^{<i>j</i>} (010)	5.4×10^{-11}

T is temperature in K. *i* and *j* are different H₂O isotopologues.

Table 4: Collisional processes affecting the O₂ vibrational level populations.

No.	Process	Rate (cm ³ s ⁻¹)
o.1	H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ , <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ H ₂ O(<i>v</i> ₁ , <i>v</i> ₂ -1, <i>v</i> ₃) + O ₂ (X,1)	$v_2 \times 1.35 \times 10^{-12}$
o.2	N ₂ (1) + O ₂ ⇌ N ₂ + O ₂ (X,1)	$6.0 \times 10^{-18} (T/300)^{1/2}$
o.3	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>) + CO ₂ (010) ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -1) + CO ₂ (001)	$3.0 \times 10^{-15} + 6.0 \times 10^{-17} \times (T-210)$
o.4	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>) + CO ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -1) + CO ₂ (020)	$1.5 \times 3.45 \times 10^{-16} \sqrt{T}$
o.5	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -1) + O(³ P)	$A \times 10^{-12} (T/315.0)^{-0.2}$
o.6	O ₂ (X,1) + M ⇌ O ₂ (X,0) + M	$4.2 \times 10^{-19} (T/300)^{1/2} v$
o.7	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> ≥ 2) + O ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -1) + O ₂ (X,1)	$B \times 10^{-13}$
o.8	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> ≥ 12) + N ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -2) + N ₂ (1)	$C \times 10^{-15}$
o.9	O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> ≥ 20) + O ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (X, <i>v</i> -1) + O ₂	$6 \times 10^{-17} (T/300) \exp(0.2v)$
o.10	O ₂ (b,2) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,2)	$1.2 \times 10^{-11} \exp(-596/T)$
o.11	O ₂ (b,1) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,1)	$4.2 \times 10^{-11} \exp(-312/T)$
o.12	O ₂ (b,2) + O ₃ ⇌ 2O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	2.9×10^{-10}
o.13	O ₂ (b,1) + O ₃ ⇌ 2O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	1.0×10^{-10}
o.14	O ₂ (b,0) + O ₃ ⇌ O ₂ (a,0) + O ₃	6.6×10^{-12}
o.15	O ₂ (b,2) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (b,1) + O(³ P)	1.1×10^{-11}
o.16	O ₂ (b,1) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (b,0) + O(³ P)	4.5×10^{-12}
o.17	O ₂ (b,0) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	2.0×10^{-14}
o.18	O ₂ (b,0) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (a,0) + O(³ P)	6.0×10^{-14}
o.19	O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (a,0) + O ₂ (X,3)	9.0×10^{-18}
o.20	O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (a,1) + O ₂ (X,2)	2.0×10^{-17}
o.21	O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (a,2) + O ₂ (X,1)	8.8×10^{-18}
o.22	O ₂ (b,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (a,3) + O ₂ (X,0)	7.4×10^{-19}
o.23	O ₂ (b,0) + N ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (a,2) + N ₂ (1)	1.05×10^{-15}
o.24	O ₂ (b,0) + N ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (X,9) + N ₂	1.05×10^{-15}
o.25	O ₂ (b,0) + CO ₂ ⇌ O ₂ (a,0) + CO ₂	4.2×10^{-13}
o.26	O ₂ (a, <i>v</i>) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (a,0) + O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>)	5.6×10^{-11}
o.27	O ₂ (a,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (X,5) + O ₂ (X0)	$5.0 \times 10^{-20} \exp(-220/T)$
o.28	O ₂ (a,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (X,4) + O ₂ (X1)	$7.7 \times 10^{-19} \exp(-220/T)$
o.29	O ₂ (a,0) + O ₂ (X,0) ⇌ O ₂ (X,3) + O ₂ (X2)	$2.8 \times 10^{-18} \exp(-220/T)$
o.30	O ₂ (a,0) + O(³ P) ⇌ O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	6.5×10^{-17}
o.31	O ₂ (a,1) + O ₃ ⇌ 2O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	4.7×10^{-12}
o.32	O ₂ (a,0) + O ₃ ⇌ 2O ₂ (X,0) + O(³ P)	$5.2 \times 10^{-11} \exp(-2840/T)$
o.33	O ₂ (a,0) + N ₂ ⇌ 2O ₂ (X,0) + N ₂	1.0×10^{-20}
o.34	O ₃ + hν → O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>) + O(³ P)	$J_{O_3}^*(X, v = 0 - 35)$
o.35	O ₃ + hν → O ₂ (a, <i>v</i>) + O(¹ D)	$J_{O_3}^*(a, v = 0 - 35)$
o.36	O ₃ + O(³ P) → O ₂ (X, <i>v</i>) + O ₂	$f_1 \times 5.6 \times 10^{-14} \exp(-1959/T)$

A = 3.2, 8.1, 2.2, for *v*=1,2,3, respectively and A = 5.0 for *v*>3.

B = 2.0, 2.6, 3.8, 2.8, 2.0, 1.5, 1.1, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.3 for *v*=1,2...11 respectively.

C = 41, 1.9, 3.7, 7.2, 14, 27, 20, 17, 14, 12, 10, 8.4, 7.1, 6.5, 4.2, 3.5, 3.2, 2.5, 2.1, 1.8, 1.5, 1.3, 1.1 for *v* = 12–35.

f₁ = 0.8, 1.9, 4.6, 9.6, 15.4, 16.1, 14.2, 7.7, 4.6, 3.5, 2.7, 2.4, 16.6 for *v*=0,1...11 respectively.

O₂(E,*v*) refers to the O₂ electronic state E and the vibrational state *v*. *T* is temperature in K.

this later production explicitly in our non-LTE model (see processes 34–36 in Table 4), but this has been commonly prescribed in models by an efficiency factor ϵ , indicating the total number of $O_2(1)$ molecules per one photodissociated O_3 molecule). A summary of the derived non-LTE parameters is shown in Table 5.

2.4.1 H_2O-O_2 NLTE uncertainties and associated errors

Several attempts have been made in the past to determine from atmospheric measurements the rate of V-V $O_2(X,1)-H_2O(v_2)$ collisions (H2O-O2-vv; processes 1 and o.1 in Tables 3 and 4, respectively), the quenching of $O_2(1)$ by atomic oxygen (O2-O-vt; process o.5 in Table 4), and the $O_2(X,1)$ production from ozone after photodissociation. A summary of the derived non-LTE parameters is shown in Table 5. We note that the values of each rate depend on the other values of the set of rates derived from each instrument and should not be used independently.

Taking into account the dispersion of the measured values (considered as sets) in Table 5 and also the temperature dependence, we have assumed the following uncertainties in the collisional rates involved in the H_2O-O_2 model:

- H2O-O2-vv: Besides the values derived from atmospheric measurements listed in Table 5, also Bass and Shields (1974), Bass et al. (1979) and Huestis (2006) provided laboratory values for the rate of V-V $O_2(X,1)-H_2O(v_2)$ collisions. Taking measured and laboratory values into account, we have estimated a 30% uncertainty.
- H2O-epsilon: We note that we consider the $O_2(X,1)$ production from ozone explicitly in our non-LTE model (see processes 34–36 in Table,4), but this has been commonly prescribed in models by an efficiency factor ϵ , indicating the total number of $O_2(1)$ molecules per one photodissociated O_3 molecule. We have assumed an uncertainty of 20% in this process.
- O2-O-vt: Besides the spread of the values derived from atmospheric measurements provided in the literature and shown in Table 5, Kalogerakis et al. (2005) and Pekajovic et al. (2011) also provided values for this kinetic rate ($3.2 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 315K and $2.9 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 295K, respectively, additionally proposing a linear and an inverse temperature dependence, respectively. We note that Copeland et al. (2009) rejected an inverse temperature dependence. Taking also into account the temperature dependence, we have estimated an overall uncertainty of 25%.
- O2-CO2-vv: The rate of O_2-CO_2 vibrational energy exchange has also been provided by Bass et al. (1973) ($9 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), Merrill and Amme ($(9 \pm 1) \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), and Cannemeyer and DeVries ($8.8 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). From all these values, we have assumed an uncertainty of 23%

2.5 CH_4 NLTE model

Table 6 summarized the collisional processes included in the CH_4 non-LTE model. The major changes included in the NLTE model regarding CH_4 ro-vibrational levels with respect to the description in Funke et al. (2012) (Table 10) are the following:

- A coefficient (c) was omitted for the rate of quenching of the bending modes ($v_b = v_4, v_2$) by N_2 and O_2 (processes 1.a, 1.b, 2.a and 2.c). The correct expression included in the NLTE model for this rate in Funke et al. (2012) should have been:

$$k_1(CH_4(v_b)-M) = v_b \exp[c(a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2)], c = 2.3$$

The update is reflected in Table 6.

Table 5: Values of the H₂O non-LTE parameters derived in the past.

Instrument	Reference	H ₂ O-O ₂ -vv(*)	O ₂ -O-vt(*)	O ₂ -CO ₂ -vv(*)	H ₂ O-epsilon
ISAMS	Zaragoza et al. (1998)	1.0-3.1	0.7-2.6	0.02-0.06	2-6
CRISTA1	Edwards et al. (2000)	1.7-3.1	0.7-1.3	–	4-6
CIRRIS	Zhou et al. (1999)		1.2		
CRISTA1	Garcia-Comas (2002)	1.7	3.0	–	5
SABER	Feofilov et al. (2009)	1.2	3.3	0.06	5-8 (z-dep)
MIPAS V8	Garcia-Comas (priv.comm.)	1.35	3.2 (300/T) ^{0.2}	0.09	implicit (z-dep)

(*) Rate given in $10^{-12}\text{cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$.

- The coefficients in the Funke et al. (2012) model regarding CH₄-O₂ V-V exchange (process 3 in Table 6) considered the rate provided by Avramides and Hunter (1983) and a fractioning taking into account the number of vibrational levels in the lower energy group of levels. Avramides and Hunter (1983) only provided the rate for relaxation from CH₄($v_3=1$ or $v_1=1$) to CH₄($v_2=1$ or $v_4=1$), i.e., only to the 7.6 μm group. More recently, Boursier et al. (2007) has provided the values at 193 K and 296 K for this rate for collisions, assuming relaxation for the 7.6 μm , 3.3 μm , 2.7 μm and 1.7 μm groups of levels only involving the v_4 upper levels. We have updated the model for CAIRT following their scheme (see Table 6, additionally taking into account the fractioning accounting for the number of levels in the lower energy group (n_s ; i.e., 2 levels for the 7.6 μm group, 2 levels for the 3.3 μm group, 3 levels for the 2.7 μm group and 1 level for the 1.7 μm group). The scheme used has little effect on the 7.6 μm levels, from which CH₄ is retrieved.
- Reaction 5 in Table 6 was not completely correct in Funke et al. (2012). The intermode exchange allowed in the model according to the expression involved all combination of levels within the v_e and the v_{e-1} groups, but it was actually allowed only between the bending (v_s) and the stretching modes (v_b) within the same group of levels v_e . The rate used was measured by Ménard-Bourcin et al. (2001), for $2v_3$.

Table 6: Collisional processes included for CH₄.

No.	Process	Rate (cm^3s^{-1})
1.a	CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)+N ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4-1)+N ₂	$2.3 \times v_4 \exp(-16 + 1.4 \times 10^{-3}T + 1.1 \times 10^{-5}T^2)$
1.b	CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)+O ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4-1)+O ₂	$2.3 \times v_4 \exp(-17.2 + 1.34 \times 10^{-2}T - 1.46 \times 10^{-5}T^2)$
2.a	CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)+N ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_1, v_2-1, v_3, v_4)+N ₂	$2.3 \times v_2 \exp(-16 + 1.4 \times 10^{-3}T + 1.1 \times 10^{-5}T^2)$
2.b	CH ₄ (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)+O ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_1, v_2-1, v_3, v_4)+O ₂	$2.3 \times v_2 \exp(-17.2 + 1.34 \times 10^{-2}T - 1.46 \times 10^{-5}T^2)$
3	CH ₄ (v_e)+O ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_e-1)+O ₂ (1)	$(1.3, 2.7, 4, 5.3) \times 10^{-13} / n_{e-1}$ for $v_e=1-4$
4	CH ₄ (v_e)+O ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ (v_e-2)+O ₂ (2)	$1.2 \times 10^{-13} / n_{e-2}$ for $v_e=2-4$
5	CH ₄ ($v_{e,i}$)+N ₂ ⇌ CH ₄ ($v_{e,i}$)+N ₂	$v_e \times 1.5 \times 10^{-11} / n_{e,j}$ for $(v_{e,i}, v_{e,j}) \in v_e=1-4$

T is temperature in K. $v_e=2v_1+v_2+2v_3+v_4$ (thus, v_e define a group of levels). n_e is number of levels in the group.

2.5.1 CH₄ NLTE uncertainties and associated errors

In our calculations, we have assumed the following uncertainties:

- **CH₄-M-vt**: The rate of quenching of the bending modes ($v_b = v_4, v_2$) by N₂ and O₂ (processes 1.a, 1.b, 2.a and 2.c in Table 6 used in the NLTE model has been taken from Siddles et al. (1994), who provided an uncertainty of 20%. Later on, Boursier et al. (2003) measured the value for collisions with N₂, obtaining $(1.2 \times 10^{-15}) \pm 33\%$ at 193K and $(3.2 \times 10^{-15}) \pm 15\%$ at 296K, and Boursier et al. (2007) measured the value for collisions with O₂ respectively, obtaining $(2.4 \times 10^{-15}) \pm 33\%$ at 193K and $(5.7 \times 10^{-15}) \pm 25\%$ at 296 K, both recommending scaling according to harmonic oscillator. We note that the temperature dependence is not the same as in Siddles et al. (1994). Avramides and Hunter (1983) also provided this rate in collisions with O₂ $(2.9 \times 10^{-15}) \pm 15\%$ at 296 K). Taking into account all measurements, including the different temperature dependence, we assume a 30% uncertainty.
- **CH₄-O₂-vv**: For CH₄-O₂ V-V exchange (process 3 in Table 6), we have assumed an uncertainty of 25%, that accounts for disagreements between available measurements of this rate (Avramides and Hunter, 1983; Boursier et al., 2007), including different temperature dependences.
- **CH₄-intermode**: The CH₄ intermode exchange (process 5 in Table 6) used was measured by Ménard-Bourcin et al. (2001) with a 30% error. Later on, Boursier et al. (2003) provided new values for v_2 and v_4 coupling, v_3 and v_1 coupling, and v_3 and v_2+v_4 coupling, all at 193K and 296K. We have considered the dispersion between these measurements and have taken the uncertainty at typical mid-mesopause temperatures (200 K), i.e., 60%.

2.6 NLTE model of other species

Other non-LTE models used in CAIRT's retrievals are those of CO and NO₂. There have been no significant changes for the non-LTE models of these species with respect to Funke et al. (2012).

2.6.1 Uncertainties in non-LTE parameters related to other species

We have assumed the following uncertainties in the collisional rates involved in the CO, N₂O and NO₂ non-LTE models:

- **CO-N₂-vv**: The rate of vibrational energy exchange between CO and N₂ ($\text{CO}(\nu) + \text{N}_2(v-1) + \text{N}_2(1)$) has been measured at atmospheric temperatures by Allen and Simpson (1980). They have also been determined by Kurnosov et al. (2010) and Hong et al. (2021). According to these values and the recommendation by Funke et al. (2007), we assume an uncertainty of 10%.
- **NO₂-M-vt**: Based on the available literature and considerations from Funke et al. (2023), the uncertainty assumed for rate of quenching of NO₂ by N₂ and O₂ has been set to 50%.

2.7 Other non-LTE related uncertainties

Apart from the kinetic rates, there are other parameters that have an important role in several non-LTE models. These are the following:

- **O-vmr**: Since the atomic oxygen is one of the dominant components of the atmosphere above the upper mesosphere, it takes part in all the non-LTE models presented here. The uncertainty associated with atomic oxygen abundance assumed is also based on García-Comas et al. (2023). To assess

the uncertainty associated with atomic oxygen below 95 km, they considered errors in ozone abundance as indicated by López-Puertas et al. (2018), a 10% uncertainty in the three-body reaction rate involved in O₃ formation, and a 5% error in ozone photodissociation. Above 95 km, they estimated the uncertainty in the atomic oxygen data by means of comparisons of WACCM data with the Naval Research Laboratory Mass Spectrometer and Incoherent Scatter radar empirical model (NRLMSIS 2.0) atomic oxygen data. These estimates were calculated separately for five distinct latitude regions, encompassing all four seasons, and accounting for both day and night conditions. On average, the uncertainties in atomic oxygen span from 25% to 30% at 85 km, gradually decreasing to 5% at 120 km, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Notably, below 85 km, particularly during nighttime, the uncertainties become significantly larger, reaching as high as 120% at 70 km.

- **N-vmr:** These encompass the uncertainties in the abundances of N(⁴S) and N(²D). These atmospheric species mainly affect the retrieval of nitric oxide. Based on the discussion by Funke et al. (2023), we have assumed a 50% uncertainty for both species abundances.
- **T120km:** This refers to the uncertainty of the temperature above 120 km, only affecting NO retrievals. We accounted for this error as a non-LTE error because the emission arising from these altitudes are entirely in non-LTE. We estimated an uncertainty of 5%, derived from the standard deviations computed for the ERS in the altitude range around 130 km, which is the emission peak of thermospheric NO.

2.8 Summary of non-LTE uncertainties

Table 7 summarizes the non-LTE uncertainties discussed and justified in the previous sections of this document. We have considered these values in the estimation of the non-LTE errors in CAIRT’s retrievals presented in the following section.

Figure 2: Average uncertainty assumed for atomic oxygen for daytime (red) and nighttime (blue). Taken from García-Comas et al. (2023).

Table 7: Summary of uncertainties in non-LTE related parameters

Abbrev.	Related parameter	Reference	Uncertainty
CO2-M-vt	NLTE CO ₂ kinetics	García-Comas et al. (2023)	30%
CO2-O-vt	NLTE CO ₂ kinetics	García-Comas et al. (2023)	50%
CO2-CO2-v2-vv	NLTE CO ₂ kinetics	García-Comas et al. (2023)	20%
CO2-M-v3-vt	NLTE CO ₂ kinetics	Jurado-Navarro et al. (2016)	15%
CO2-N2-v3-vv	NLTE CO ₂ kinetics	Jurado-Navarro et al. (2016)	5%
NO-O-vib	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	20%
NO-O-rot	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	25%
NO-O-spin	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	50K
NO-O2	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	20%
NO2+hv	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	10%
NO2+O	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	40%
RT-beta	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	5%
RT-O	NLTE NO kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	50%
O3-O-vt	NLTE O ₃ kinetics	López-Puertas et al. (2023)	50%
O3-M-vt	NLTE O ₃ kinetics	López-Puertas et al. (2023)	20%
O3+hv	NLTE O ₃ kinetics	López-Puertas et al. (2023)	7%
O+O2+M	NLTE O ₃ kinetics	López-Puertas et al. (2023)	10%
H2O-O2-vv	NLTE H ₂ O kinetics	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	30%
O2-CO2-vv	NLTE H ₂ O kinetics	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	23%
H2O-epsilon	NLTE H ₂ O & CH ₄ kin.	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	20%
O2-O-vt	NLTE H ₂ O & CH ₄ kin.	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	25%
CH4-M-vt	NLTE CH ₄ kinetics	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	30%
CH4-intermode	NLTE CH ₄ kinetics	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	60%
CH4-O2-vv	NLTE CH ₄ kinetics	García-Comas [priv. comm.]	25%
NO2-M-vt	NLTE NO ₂ kinetics	Funke et al. (2023)	50%
CO-N2-vv	NLTE CO kinetics	Funke et al. (2007)	10%
vmr_O	O uncertainty	García-Comas et al. (2023)	height-dependent*
vmr_N	N(4S), N(2D) uncert.	Funke et al. (2023)	50%
T120km	T (>120km) uncert.	ERS climatology	5%

* See Fig. 2.

3 Impact on CAIRT's target quantities

In order to estimate the error in CAIRT's L2 targets associated to the non-LTE parameter uncertainties listed in Table 7, we performed calculations for each parameter uncertainty using the 2D Linear Performance Estimator (LPEv2) within SciRec (see detailed description in Sect. 1.3 in DEL-08-CAIRT-Ph0SciRec). To this end, we used the ERS climatologies. Figures 3-29 in the Appendix of this document (Sect. 4) show the individual contribution of the non-LTE parameter uncertainties on the retrieved quantities averaged over all ERS atmospheres. We have summarized the results for each target in Table 8 in the context of CAIRT's L2 uncertainty requirements. We compared the target requirements with the error associated to each non-LTE parameter uncertainty and used the following color code:

- Green: the associated non-LTE error is smaller than the goal requirement at all heights.
- Lime: At some height, the associated non-LTE error is larger than the goal requirement but smaller than 0.8 times the threshold requirement.
- Yellow: At some height, the associated non-LTE error is larger than 0.8 times the threshold requirement but smaller than 1.2 times the threshold requirement.
- Orange: At some height, the associated non-LTE error is larger than 1.2 times the threshold requirement.

The 'Total' column follows the same color code and refers to the total non-LTE error (root sum square of the individual non-LTE errors). Note that the metrics applied here is more stringent than what is used to evaluate the overall uncertainty (Figure 4 of D08-CAIRT-Ph0SciRec) as it evaluates climatological average uncertainties at individual altitudes, rather than averaged over vertical ranges.

There are three L2 targets that will benefit from improvements in the non-LTE uncertainties:

- Temperature: The uncertainty in the rate of quenching of $\text{CO}_2(v_2)$ by atomic oxygen (CO2-O-vt) leads to temperature errors larger than 1.2 times the threshold requirement, but only at 112-115 km (see Fig. 3 in the Appendix). This compromises CAIRT's uncertainty requirements at those altitudes. Therefore, the reduction of the uncertainty in this rate is would be highly beneficial.
- Nitric oxide: NO-O-vib, NO-O-spin and NO2+hv uncertainties produce errors larger than the goal requirement but smaller than 0.8 times the threshold requirement. The propagation of the temperature error due to uncertainties in CO2-O-vt onto the retrieved NO, the NO-O-rot uncertainty and the uncertainty in temperature above 120 km, each individually, lead to NO errors within 0.8 and $1.2 \times$ threshold requirement at 95 km, and within the goal and $0.8 \times$ threshold requirements at 65–75 km, 85–95 km and 110–115 km (see Fig. 5). Nevertheless, these addition of these contributions lead to NO errors larger than 1.2 times the threshold error around 95 km. Therefore, the reduction of the uncertainty of any (or all) of these later three non-LTE error sources would be of benefit.
- Carbon monoxide: The propagation of the temperature error due to uncertainties in CO2-O-vt onto the retrieved CO is larger than the goal requirement but smaller than 0.8 times the threshold requirement and only at 105–115 km (see Fig. 6). Therefore, reducing the CO2-O-vt uncertainty would also benefit the CO retrieval.

In summary, the CO2-O-vt uncertainty is seen as the most relevant non-LTE errors source. Therefore, the reduction of this uncertainty by means of more precise laboratory measurements would be of high value for guaranteeing that CAIRT's L2 target uncertainty requirements can even be met in the 112-115 km range.

	CO2-M-vt	CO2-O-vt	CO2-CO2-v2-vv	CO2-M-v3-vt	CO2-N2-v3-vv	vmr_O	NO-O-vib	NO-O-rot	NO-O-spin	NO-O2	NO2+hv	NO2+O	RT-beta	RT-O	T120km	vmr_N	NO2-M-vt	O3-O-vt	O3-Oeq	O3-M-vt	O+O2+M	CO-N2-vv	H2O-epsilon	H2O-O2-vv	O2-CO2-vv	O2-O-vt	CH4-M-vt	CH4-intermode	CH4-O2-vv	Total
Tem.	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
O ₃	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
NO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
CO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
NO ₂	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
H ₂ O	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
CH ₄	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
N ₂ O	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
HNO ₃	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
N ₂ O ₅	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
ClONO ₂	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
CFC11	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
CFC12	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
SF ₆	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
HCN	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
SO ₂	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
C ₂ H ₂	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
C ₂ H ₆	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
PAN	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
NH ₃	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
H ₂ SO ₄	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
NH ₄ NO ₃	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
HCOOH	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
HCFC22	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
OCS	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

Table 8: Summary of non-LTE errors in CAIRT's L2 quantities. Green: NLTE-error < goal requirement, at all heights. Lime: goal < NLTE-error < 0.8 × threshold requirement, at some height. Yellow: 0.8 × threshold < NLTE-error < 1.2 × threshold, at some height. Orange: NLTE-error < 1.2 × threshold, at some height. The 'Total' column refers to the root sum square of the individual non-LTE errors.

4 Appendix

Figures 3-29 show the individual contribution of the non-LTE parameter uncertainties on the retrieved quantities averaged over all ERS atmospheres. Note that, for each species, we do not show the effect of the uncertainties of all the non-LTE parameters, but only the main candidates. Contributions from the ones not shown do not contribute significantly.

Figure 3: Mean contribution of the non-LTE parameter uncertainties on the retrieved temperatures. The green area limits the goal requirement, the yellow area limits 0.8 times the threshold requirement, the orange area limits $1.2 \times$ the threshold requirement, and the red area is beyond $1.2 \times$ the threshold requirement.

Figure 4: As Fig. 3 but for O₃.

Figure 5: As Fig. 3 but for NO.

Figure 6: As Fig. 3 but for CO.

Figure 7: As Fig. 3 but for NO₂.

Figure 8: As Fig. 3 but for H₂O.

Figure 9: As Fig. 3 but for CH₄.

Figure 10: As Fig. 3 but for N₂O.

Figure 11: As Fig. 3 but for HNO₃.

Figure 12: As Fig. 3 but for N₂O₅.

Figure 13: As Fig. 3 but for CIONO₂.

Figure 14: As Fig. 3 but for N₂O₅.

Figure 15: As Fig. 3 but for CLONO₂.

Figure 16: As Fig. 3 but for CFC-11.

Figure 17: As Fig. 3 but for CFC-12.

Figure 18: As Fig. 3 but for SF₆.

Figure 19: As Fig. 3 but for HCN.

Figure 20: As Fig. 3 but for SO₂.

Figure 21: As Fig. 3 but for C₂H₂.

Figure 22: As Fig. 3 but for C₂H₆.

Figure 23: As Fig. 3 but for PAN.

Figure 24: As Fig. 3 but for NH₃.

Figure 25: As Fig. 3 but for H₂SO₄-liquid.

Figure 26: As Fig. 3 but for NH₄NO₃-solid.

Figure 27: As Fig. 3 but for HCOOH.

Figure 28: As Fig. 3 but for HCF-22.

Figure 29: As Fig. 3 but for OCS.

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